

Lightweight Human Gesture Recognition Using Multimodal Features

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Abstract—Human gesture recognition is a very important tool in human-computer or human-robot interaction. In many cases, such algorithms may need to be executed on systems with limited computational capabilities, due to size or weight constraints, introducing restrictions that can impede gesture recognition performance. This paper proposes a gesture recognition method that is based on a very simple and lightweight Deep Neural Network (DNN) architecture, suitable for embedded execution. In order to achieve increased accuracy without a large computational/memory overhead, the proposed method utilizes as input both full 2D human body skeletons and image patches extracted from regions of interest (e.g., around human arms) in each video frame. These two input types are processed in parallel by separate modules and the corresponding features are fused before being exploited for gesture recognition. Reliance on 2D skeleton sequences allows the utilization of a lightweight DNN architecture, while the image patches convey rich semantic information that enhances gesture recognition performance. This approach is unlike existing similar methods, which only exploit skeleton sequences. Experimental evaluation indeed shows increased recognition accuracy, indicating that the proposed method offers a reliable solution for human gesture recognition on embedded systems.

Index Terms—Gesture Recognition, Multimodal Features, LSTMs, Video Descriptors

I. INTRODUCTION

Human gesture recognition involves analyzing input data sequences (typically RGB or RGB-D videos) to recognize a set of gestures performed by a person, and plays a crucial role in a wide range of human-computer/robot interaction applications [1], [2]. For example, gesture recognition can be utilized to control an Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) [1] or to use a computer [3] through gestures. Nevertheless, gesture recognition faces considerable challenges when it is employed on systems operating in real-world conditions. For instance, with RGB video inputs [4], illumination conditions, viewpoint variations and distance between the person and the camera

may dramatically affect the achieved recognition accuracy. Another challenge stems from execution on embedded systems with limited computational capabilities, which may still need to support predictions obtained in real-time.

Previous gesture recognition approaches [1], [5]–[8] mostly rely on analyzing sequences of 2D/3D skeletons pre-extracted from the RGB videos (e.g., per-frame), rather than the RGB videos themselves. This is mainly due to two reasons: a) 2D/3D skeletons can be easily and accurately extracted from the input videos by utilizing off-the-shelf 2D/3D human pose estimation methods [9]–[11], and b), 2D/3D skeletons can be analyzed much faster than RGB videos. Such skeleton-based methods, therefore, typically consist of two consecutive stages: the 2D/3D skeleton extraction stage and the gesture recognition stage. While the first one usually comprises Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), the Deep Neural Networks (DNNs) employed in the second stage vary. For example, [1] utilizes Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks to analyze the extracted skeleton sequences, while [8], [12] exploit a Graph Convolutional Network (GCN).

Therefore, such approaches aim to recognize gestures by exclusively processing the available skeleton sequences, discarding all visual appearance information contained within the input RGB content. However this approach is not optimal, since the extracted skeletons are only a rough representation of the human body, as they consist only of a specific, predefined set of body joints (e.g., shoulders, wrists, knees, etc.). Certain gestures that involve finer motions, such as finger movements or very small displacements (slight body joint rotations/translations) cannot be distinguished effectively between each other. While methods that include palm/finger joints in the 2D/3D skeletons [13] could offer a sufficient solution, their predictions can only be trusted when the person performing the gestures is really close to the camera and his/her fingers are clearly visible. In real-world scenarios, this is rarely the case.

This paper proposes a gesture recognition method that

analyzes both 2D skeleton sequences and visual information obtained from the input RGB videos to output accurate predictions. This is achieved by introducing a novel architecture that augments existing skeleton-based ones with an *appearance-based feature extractor*, which analyzes only specific regions of the input video frames. This additional module is specifically designed to provide rich information to the overall DNN, obtained by the visual cues, while adding minimum computational overhead. It relies on a neural implementation of the Frame Moments Descriptor (FMod) and its local variant LMoD [14]–[16], which can effectively encode local visual information by efficiently capturing the most informative input appearance statistics. Thus, the proposed appearance-based feature extractor is a plug-and-play module *without any learnable parameters* that can be used to enhance the performance of existing lightweight skeleton-based methods.

Experimental evaluation on two gesture recognition datasets shows that the proposed method increases the gesture recognition accuracy compared to the baseline. Moreover, integrating the proposed FMod-powered appearance-based feature extractor within the overall gesture recognition architecture is more effective than using a learnable CNN feature extractor in its place.

II. RELATED WORK

Skeleton-based gesture recognition methods [5]–[7], [17]–[19] overcome the challenges encountered in RGB video-based methods (e.g., due to lighting conditions and/or scale variations) by processing the corresponding, precomputed per-frame human body skeletons, which do not suffer from the aforementioned appearance variations, instead of the raw RGB video input. The human skeletons can be obtained via human pose estimation methods [10], [20], [21] that analyze the RGB video in a preprocessing step. Following this approach, several gesture/action recognition methods utilize 3D human skeletons [5], [6], [22] to capture joint dependencies in 3D space and extract features for action/gesture recognition. However, using 3D skeleton sequences as input can be problematic due to scale, rotation and translation variations.

On the other hand, accurate 2D skeletons can be extracted from RGB videos using 2D human pose estimation methods [10], [20], offering a more reliable data source for action/gesture recognition than 3D skeletons. To this end, [17] utilizes 2D skeletons to compute motion features and combines them with appearance features in order to achieve increased action recognition performance. Similarly, 2D skeletons are utilized in [7] to encode slow and fast body joint movements within an action and compute pairwise body joint distances, which are exploited to improve action recognition performance. Moreover, the method in [23] also relies on 2D skeletons, which are processed by a two-stream network to recognize actions even under heavy occlusions.

Methodologically, early relevant DNNs utilized Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) [24], [25] or CNNs [26], [27] to analyze the 2D skeleton sequences. For example, DD-Net [7] uses a lightweight CNN to process 2D human skeleton

data sequences in order to recognize actions. Later, many methods relying on LSTMs [1], [23], [24] demonstrated superior performance. For example, a hierarchical LSTM network architecture in [24] separately models the temporal dynamics of the lower-body and the upper-body, which are subsequently combined together to obtain the final predictions. Similarly, a two-branch stacked LSTM network architecture for action recognition is introduced in [23], which acts on 2D human skeletons.

With the rise of Graph Convolutional Networks (GCNs) [28], 2D or 3D skeletons could also be represented as graphs, resulting in more flexible and efficient models [5], [6], [12], [22]. For example, the method in [22] represents the human skeleton as a directed acyclic graph that is subsequently utilized within a Directed Graph Neural Network (DGNN) to compute features for action recognition. Spatio-Temporal Graph Convolutional Network (ST-GCN) [8], [12] utilizes GCNs to encode both spatial and temporal information from human graph sequences, thus increasing action/gesture recognition accuracy. Finally, Transformer architectures [29] have also been employed for action/gesture recognition, managing to achieve state-of-the-art performance.

Moving towards a different direction, the method proposed in this paper augments existing skeleton-based gesture recognition pipelines with an appearance-based local feature extractor, which allows the DNN to exploit additional visual information without burdening its training with any additional learnable parameters.

III. GESTURE RECOGNITION USING MULTI-MODAL FEATURES

Let $\mathcal{S} = \{\mathbf{S}_1, \dots, \mathbf{S}_L\} \in \mathbb{R}^{L \times W \times H \times 3}$ be an input RGB image sequence, where L is the length of the sequence and W, H are the image width and height respectively, depicting a person that performs a series of gestures. The ultimate goal of the proposed method presented in Fig. 1 is to effectively analyze this sequence to extract rich features which allow the accurate recognition of all the performed gestures.

In this direction, two types of features are extracted. First, a CNN is utilized to extract the person’s 2D skeleton from each RGB image in the input sequence, calculating a 2D skeleton sequence $\mathcal{P} = \{\mathbf{P}_1, \dots, \mathbf{P}_L\} \in \mathbb{R}^{L \times N \times 2}$ that comprises the corresponding 2D pixel coordinates of a pre-defined set of N body joints (e.g., shoulders, wrists, knees, etc.). However, since gestures may be performed using only specific body parts (e.g., arms or hands), the extracted 2D skeleton sequence is further processed to obtain $\tilde{\mathcal{P}} = \{\tilde{\mathbf{P}}_1, \dots, \tilde{\mathbf{P}}_L\} \in \mathbb{R}^{L \times M \times 2}$, $M < N$, which contains only the 2D pixel coordinates of the relevant M body joints. This ensures attention is focused solely on the body joints of interest, thus reducing the burden on the overall DNN by avoiding the processing of redundant features that may introduce noise (e.g., due to imperfect 2D skeleton predictions). Therefore, if f_{CNN} denotes the 2D skeleton extraction CNN, the calculation of $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}$ proceeds as:

$$\mathbf{P}_i = f_{CNN}(\mathbf{S}_i) \quad (1)$$

Fig. 1. The overall architecture of the proposed method.

and

$$\tilde{\mathbf{P}}_i = \text{joint_proc}(\mathbf{P}_i). \quad (2)$$

The CNN employed to extract 2D skeletons from each RGB image is an improved version of the multi-branch CNN proposed in [9], where the simple interbranch skip connections were replaced with more powerful cross-attention [30] synapses. Note that since in the scope of this paper all gestures are performed by the person’s upper body, $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}$ considers only the wrists, elbows, shoulders, and head joints, resulting in $M = 7$ body joints.

Besides providing important spatiotemporal information, the first type of features $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}$ also serve an additional purpose. That is, they are utilized to define the regions-of-interest (ROIs) on the input RGB images. Therefore, after $\tilde{\mathbf{P}}_i$ is obtained, the 2D pixel coordinates of the body joints extracted from each input image are utilized to define a rectangular ROI of fixed size on the corresponding image that encloses all of them. In the context of this work, the “head” body joint is excluded from this process, essentially resulting in a hand patch extraction process (since all the remaining body joints in $\tilde{\mathbf{P}}_i$ correspond to the person’s wrists, elbows and shoulders). Therefore, for each input image the corresponding hand patches are extracted and concatenated, forming a hand patch sequence $\mathcal{H} = \{\mathbf{H}_1, \dots, \mathbf{H}_L\} \in \mathbb{R}^{L \times W' \times H' \times 3}$, where W' , H' are the width and the height of the concatenated hand image patches \mathbf{H}_i , respectively.

The extracted hand patch sequence \mathcal{H} is subsequently fed to the appearance-based feature extractor to calculate the second type of features $\tilde{\mathcal{H}}$ that encode rich visual information. To this end, the proposed appearance-based feature extractor utilizes at its core a neural implementation [16] of the local variant [15] of FMoD [14], which is denoted as f_{FMoD} . FMoD operates by iteratively dissecting an input frame into segments

and calculating statistical properties for each compartment. Therefore, the proposed descriptor starts by partitioning each hand patch \mathbf{H}_i into four blocks and calculating eight statistical properties for each block. Then, each of the four blocks is further partitioned into four sub-blocks and the same statistical properties are again calculated. This process can be continued for multiple partitioning levels, as illustrated in Fig. 2. The statistical properties calculated for each block comprise the row-wise and the column-wise mean μ , standard deviation σ , skewness β_1 and kurtosis β_2 , resulting in a vector $\mathbf{u} = [\mu_r, \sigma_r, \beta_{1r}, \beta_{2r}, \mu_c, \sigma_c, \beta_{1c}, \beta_{2c}]$, where subscripts r and c denote the row-wise and the column-wise calculated properties, respectively. If l denotes the total number of the partition levels, then the proposed f_{FMoD} calculates $K = \sum_{i=1}^l 4^i$ vectors $\mathbf{u}_k \in \mathbb{R}^8$, $k = 1, \dots, K$. All vectors \mathbf{u}_k calculated for a hand patch \mathbf{H}_i can then be concatenated to form $\tilde{\mathbf{H}}_i \in \mathbb{R}^{K \times 8}$, and thus the visual features extracted by the appearance-based feature extractor for the entire sequence can be written as $\tilde{\mathcal{H}} = \{\tilde{\mathbf{H}}_1, \dots, \tilde{\mathbf{H}}_L\} \in \mathbb{R}^{L \times K \times 8}$. Therefore, the overall calculation of $\tilde{\mathcal{H}}$ proceeds as:

$$\mathbf{H}_i = \text{patch_extract}(\mathbf{S}_i, \tilde{\mathbf{P}}_i) \quad (3)$$

and

$$\tilde{\mathbf{H}}_i = f_{FMoD}(\mathbf{H}_i). \quad (4)$$

Note that in the proposed method $l = 2$ has been selected, in order to minimize the computational burden.

With both types of features ($\tilde{\mathcal{P}}$ and $\tilde{\mathcal{H}}$) available, the proposed method proceeds to the final gesture recognition step. To this end, the two types of features are fused before given to the final gesture recognition DNN, denoted as f_G . The feature fusion process involves reshaping both $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}$ and $\tilde{\mathcal{H}}$ so that $\tilde{\mathcal{P}} \in \mathbb{R}^{L \times 2M}$ and $\tilde{\mathcal{H}} \in \mathbb{R}^{L \times 8K}$ and then concatenating them across the first dimension resulting in $\mathcal{F} = \tilde{\mathcal{P}} \parallel \tilde{\mathcal{H}} \in \mathbb{R}^{L \times 2M + 8K}$,

Fig. 2. The partitioning process followed by f_{FmoD} .

where \parallel denotes the concatenation operation. Note that $\tilde{\mathcal{H}}$ are further refined using two fully-connected layers before given to the feature fusion process. Finally, the fused features \mathcal{F} are given as input to the gesture recognition DNN f_G , which consists of a simple LSTM and two fully-connected layers, in order to predict the final gesture label \hat{g} :

$$\hat{g} = f_G(\text{fusion}(\tilde{\mathcal{P}}, \tilde{\mathcal{H}})). \quad (5)$$

The overall architecture (Fig. 1) is trained in an end-to-end manner using a typical Cross Entropy loss function. Note that the 2D skeleton extraction CNN f_{CNN} is kept frozen during the whole training process.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

The proposed method is evaluated using two gesture recognition datasets. The first dataset is the AUTH-GESTURE dataset [31], which consists of 4930 videos (80/20 split for training and testing) of six gestures (Cross arms, Extend one arm to the side, Palms together, Raise one arm upwards, Thumps up, V shape). It is a very challenging dataset due to large viewpoint variations and the fact that three of the six gestures (Raise one arm upwards, Thumps up, V shape) appear very similar. The second dataset is the UAV-Gesture dataset [32], which is composed of 119 UAV-captured videos, containing 13 gestures performed by 10 subjects in total.

The proposed framework was trained for 200 epochs, using the SGD optimizer. The batch size was set to 32, while the learning rate was fixed to 10^{-4} . All training and experiments have been implemented in Python using a computer equipped with an NVIDIA GTX 1080 GPU.

The proposed method has been evaluated following two protocols. The first one (P-I) assumes that the entire input RGB image sequence \mathcal{S} depicts a single and complete gesture, while the second protocol (P-II) assumes that at least the last 80% of the RGB images in the sequence correspond to the gesture of interest, simulating a more realistic scenario.

TABLE I
COMPARISON ON BOTH EVALUATION PROTOCOLS (P-I AND P-II) USING THE AUTH-GESTURE DATASET [31].

Model	Accuracy	
	P-I	P-II
<i>DDNet</i> [7]	74.18 %	52.41 %
<i>RGR</i> [1]	75.83%	62.51%
<i>MMGR</i> $_{\tilde{\mathcal{P}}}$	77.08%	64.94%
<i>MMGR</i> $_{CNN}$	77.17%	67.06%
<i>MMGR</i>	77.74%	70.37%

TABLE II
COMPARISON ON BOTH EVALUATION PROTOCOLS (P-I AND P-II) USING THE UAV-GESTURE DATASET [32].

Model	Accuracy	
	P-I	P-II
<i>DDNet</i> [7]	91.51 %	69.03 %
<i>RGR</i> [1]	92.62 %	66.35%
<i>MMGR</i> $_{\tilde{\mathcal{P}}}$	92.25%	62.94%
<i>MMGR</i> $_{CNN}$	90.77%	69.87%
<i>MMGR</i>	93.73%	74.06%

The proposed method, denoted as *MMGR*, is compared against two state-of-the-art skeleton-based gesture recognition methods *DDNet* [7] and *RGR* [1]. Moreover, an ablation study has been performed where the main version of the proposed method is compared against two variants: a) one where the proposed appearance-based feature extractor is replaced by a learnable shallow CNN with two convolutional layers (*MMGR* $_{CNN}$), and b) one where the features $\tilde{\mathcal{H}}$ are not considered at all (*MMGR* $_{\tilde{\mathcal{P}}}$).

The comparison results for the AUTH-GESTURE dataset are presented in Table I. It can be seen that the proposed method outperforms all competing methods in both evaluation protocols. Importantly, the proposed method increases the gesture recognition accuracy by at least 7% when compared to *RGR* and *DDNet* in the more realistic evaluation protocol (P-II), thus offering a more reliable solution for real-world applications. Moreover, when evaluated on the UAV-GESTURE dataset, it again demonstrates increased gesture recognition performance in both evaluation protocols, as it can be seen in Table II.

Overall, the comparison results presented in Tables I and II indicate that the multimodal features extracted by the proposed method allow a very simple gesture recognizer to produce accurate predictions. Finally, since *MMGR* outperforms both *MMGR* $_{CNN}$ and *MMGR* $_{\tilde{\mathcal{P}}}$ variants, it is shown that the proposed appearance-based feature extractor is able to encode rich visual information that is necessary for accurate gesture recognition.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents a gesture recognition DNN architecture that relies on multimodal features to achieve increased gesture recognition accuracy, while using a very simple gesture recognizer. The proposed method augments a common two-stage skeleton-based gesture recognition architecture with an appearance-based feature extractor, which enriches the skeleton-derived features with local visual information encoded from the input RGB video frames. The proposed appearance-based feature extractor relies on the FMod/LMod image/video descriptor and does not come with any learnable parameters; thus it can be used as a plug-and-play module to enrich the extracted features. Experiments on two gesture recognition datasets show that the proposed method achieves increased gesture recognition accuracy, offering a reliable solution for real-world gesture recognition scenarios. Moreover, an ablation study has verified the effectiveness of the proposed appearance-based feature extractor.

Future work includes augmenting Transformer-based architectures with the proposed appearance-based feature extractor and adding learnable parameters to it to further increase its effectiveness.

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